

LOCAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP ENTITIES' DEVELOPMENT AND THE UTILIZATION OF THEIR EXPORT POTENTIAL.

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, local economist Kh.P. Abulqosimov has scientifically substantiated that "the expansion of the export potential of entrepreneurship entities can be achieved through the establishment of an appropriate business environment by the state, which ensures sufficient opportunities for utilizing their production capacity based on the free operation of entrepreneurial entities within the country." According to the scholar's research, particularly at the initial stages of small business development, the improvement of state programs aimed at protecting the economic interests of entrepreneurship entities contributes to the expansion of their activities, which ultimately leads to the formation of export potential.

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Similar scientific conclusions are reflected in the research findings of another local economist, F.N. Boyboboeva, who argues that "through the effective resolution of issues related to economic security in the activities of entrepreneurship entities, their development tendencies accelerate, resulting first in increased competitiveness within domestic markets and subsequently in the growth of production volumes of highly competitive goods for foreign markets, thereby ensuring the effective utilization of the export potential of entrepreneurial entities." During the research process, the scholar emphasized the necessity of identifying both positive and negative factors affecting entrepreneurial activity according to the specific directions of business operations.

At the same time, M.P. Eshov developed scientific proposals and practical recommendations concerning the priorities for sectoral development through the study of

issues related to the application of tax and customs incentives, preferential lending mechanisms, and state preferences as part of modern support instruments formed under state programs aimed at developing entrepreneurial activity and increasing the efficiency of utilizing export potential under contemporary conditions of economic development. The significance of this research lies in its contribution to evaluating the impact of the growing export potential of entrepreneurial entities on the macroeconomic stability of the national economy as a consequence of the expansion of entrepreneurial activity.

In particular, N.A. Imomova conducted scientific research on increasing the role of entrepreneurship entities in the country's industrial sector through the establishment of import-substituting and export-oriented production within the framework of ongoing industrialization reforms in Uzbekistan. The results of this research indicate that the consistent expansion of production volumes resulting from the active development of entrepreneurship entities across various industrial sectors may ultimately contribute to the enhancement of their export potential.

Another local economist, O.A. Aripov, comparatively analyzed the practices of developed countries regarding the organization of entrepreneurial activity in the form of small business and the improvement of export potential utilization efficiency, while also developing scientific proposals and practical recommendations for their creative adaptation to the conditions of Uzbekistan. The scientific conclusions obtained in this research substantiate that, due to the relatively weaker competitiveness of small entrepreneurial entities compared to large enterprises in export activities, a differentiated state support mechanism should be introduced for export-oriented businesses. In other words, state-provided incentives and preferences aimed at increasing the efficiency of export potential utilization should be implemented to a greater extent for small entrepreneurship entities than for medium and large business entities.

Furthermore, S.K. Salaev conducted scientific research aimed at improving the efficiency of entrepreneurship entities operating in the agricultural sector, taking into account the high level of agricultural specialization within the sectoral structure of the national economy. According to the scholar's findings, "the establishment of cooperatives based on foreign experience in strengthening integration relations among entrepreneurship entities within agro-industrial sectors in rural areas contributes to increasing the efficiency of utilizing the export potential of entrepreneurial entities."

It should also be emphasized that recent reforms implemented in the country have focused on increasing the innovative activity of entrepreneurship entities and improving production efficiency in order to ensure the effective utilization of export potential. Strategic objectives and priorities in this sphere have been developed, while the regulation of relations associated with innovative activity is based on the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Innovative Activity." In particular, the priorities for developing innovative activities and innovative production by entrepreneurship entities are reflected in the "Innovation Development Strategy." The adoption of regulatory and legal documents aimed at increasing the efficiency of export potential utilization on the basis of innovation theories has significantly intensified the interest of local economists in conducting scientific research in this direction. At the same time, these legal and regulatory acts have further increased the

importance of innovation in enhancing the effectiveness of utilizing the export potential of local entrepreneurial entities.

Alongside this, the adoption of the “Digital Uzbekistan – 2030” Strategy has led to the implementation of large-scale reforms aimed at creating favorable conditions for entrepreneurship entities to utilize digital services, improving the business environment, and reducing bureaucratic procedures. As a result, processes related to the integration of entrepreneurship entities into the digitalized platforms of international markets have expanded, thereby contributing to the enhancement of export potential utilization efficiency. This, in turn, has increased the interest of local economists in conducting scientific research focused on improving the efficiency of export potential utilization in the context of digital economy development in Uzbekistan. It is particularly important to note that economic studies have scientifically proven that the use of digital technologies in organizing production processes by entrepreneurship entities creates opportunities for significantly reducing production costs.

Based on the above analysis, it can be concluded that as the level of development of entrepreneurial activity in the national economy continues to increase, reforms aimed at improving the efficiency of utilizing export potential are becoming increasingly significant. It should also be emphasized that the constitutional закрепление of entrepreneurial freedoms, property inviolability, and socio-economic relations related to entrepreneurial activity demonstrates the priority status of this sector within the country’s economy..

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